

Effect of Toposequence on Land Suitability for Yam (*Dioscorea Spp*) Cultivation in Amanyi-Nta, Ihitte/Uboma Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Yam is one of the chief sources of carbohydrates. There is large prospect in growing yam as a way of diversifying crops, to ensure food security. The major issue in the study area is the highly undulating nature of the land. Nutrients' concentrations vary across an undulating landscape, which will require varying management options. Thus, the study evaluated the effect of the slope positions on the suitability of the land for yam cultivation. One soil profile was dug at the upper, middle and lower slope positions of the toposequence (Total: 3 Soil Profiles). The soil profiles and their environs were morphologically described. The soil horizons identified were sampled for the laboratory analysis of the chemical and physical properties. The morphological examinations revealed various shade of brownish coloration of the soils while structure was dominated by granular and crumb, then sub-angular blocky in the surface and subsurface layers of the pedons, respectively. The bulk densities were moderate while the soil moisture contents were low. The soil pH varied between 5 and 6 while the exchangeable cations were all lower than 3.00 cmol kg⁻¹. The pedons were moderately suitable for yam cultivation with varying management options due to the varying landscapes, which include making of big heaps in the lowers slopes, as well as the incorporation of organic matter in the upper and middle slope positions.

Keywords: Toposequence, Yam, Food security, Land suitability, Soil profile, Pedon.

Introduction

One of the major challenges of the developing nations is food insecurity. This is associated with low yield of cultivated

areas. Most of the cultivated lands are inherently poor in fertility due to some natural phenomena. Topography as a natural phenomenon is one of the factors of soil

formation (Brady and Weil, 2002). As a factor of soil formation, this means that it exerts direct influence on the morphological, physical and chemical properties of soils that are formed. As far back as 1958, Jenny postulated that topography severely modifies the other factors of soil formation. Hence, it can also be considered as an independent factor of soil formation (Toposequence). Topography can also manipulate climate which is readily seen expressed in the vegetation of north- and south-facing slopes. The research findings by Yannis *et al.* (2016) showed that the steepness of a topography can influence soil erosion because of the effects of washing or blowing soil materials, which affects the fertility of top soils. Influence of topography is also seen in broad river deltas. Crests of natural levees near the stream channels have coarser material than the areas beyond the levees that are very nearly level and have the finer textured initial materials (Samndi and Adamu, 2010). In steeper topography where the valleys below the mountain ranges are characterized by broad alluvial-colluvial fans, the initial material near the mountain range contains more coarse and angular material than areas farther away from the mountain range (Buol *et al.*, 1973).

According to IITA (2013), most of the world's production of yam comes from West Africa representing 94%, with Nigeria alone

producing 71%. African countries imported more than 2,000 tons in 2002, and exported 15,500, of which Nigeria exported 12% (IITA, 2013). In Nigeria, yam contributes more than 200 dietary calories per day for over 60 million people (Bassey, 2017). One of the major challenges that face yam cultivation in Nigeria has been reported to be decline in soil fertility (Bassey, 2017). Following the scarcity of fertilizer, the best alternative is to choose sites that are highly or moderately suitable for the cultivation of yam. Akamigbo (2010) defined soil suitability as the fitness of a given type of land for a defined use, which may be considered in its present condition or after improvements. Thus, the suitability of a given piece of land is its natural ability to support a specific purpose.

Tubers are an alternative source of foodstuffs containing carbohydrates. Tubers have strategic potential as a food reserve in the future. However, the role of tubers in food consumption is noticeably decreasing in line with the consumption pattern of the community which focuses on cassava. Researchers have reported that the protein percentage of yam is 12 % per higher than cassava per 100 g (Chikezie *et al.*, 2016). This is advantage of yam over cassava with respect to diet-balancing. Other advantages yam has over cassava include 2.28 % more of fibre, 21.05 % more of vitamin K, 10.62

% more of vitamin A, 6.25 % more of calcium, and 70.59 % less of sugar content, all per 100 g (Versus, 2024). Over time, there has been observation that cultivation of yam is declining which may be attributed to the uncertainty of yield due to the variation in the productivity of soils following the varying soil physical and chemical properties along the toposequences. There is also observed dearth of information on yam suitability and management options at various topo-positions along toposequences. Therefore, there is urgent need to evaluate the effects of toposequence on the soil morphological, physical and chemical properties for yam cultivation, targeting also the second Sustainable Development Goal (zero hunger). Thus, the general objective of this research was to determine the effect of toposequence on land suitability for yam (*Dioscorea spp*) cultivation in Amanyi-nta, Ihitte/uboma Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Description of Study Area

Amanyi-nta is located in Ihitte/Uboma Local Government Area which lies within latitudes 4°45'N and 7°15'N and Longitude 6°50'E and 7°25'E and is located in Imo state, Nigeria (Plate 1). The climate of the area is typical of tropical humid region with annual rainfall varying from 1990 to 2200 mm, a mean annual temperature of above 20°C and an average annual relative humidity of 75% (Ukabiala and Obazi, 2022). The soils of the area are formed from the Tertiary Coastal Plain Sands (Ukabiala *et al.*, 2016). The area is strongly undulating in most parts, with depressions to streams. The soil is under secondary rainforest vegetation. The cropping system practiced in the area includes rotational bush fallow and mixed cropping. Cassava is grown at the upland. Plate 1 shows the vegetation at the lower slope position, dominated by bamboo trees and wild cocoyam. Erosion has transported a lot of materials including plastics to the lower slope position. This has led to plastic pollution at the lower slope position of the toposequence (Plate 1).

Plate 1 Vegetation and plastic pollution at the lower slope position of Amainyi-nta Toposequence

Data Collection

The sampling adopted a free survey technique. In this method, three slope positions were identified, following the physiography of the land. The slope positions were denoted as Upper Slope (A), Middle Slope (B) and Lower Slope (C). These are shown in Plates 2 to 4. One profile pit was dug in each unit to represent the pedon. Profile A was dug to the depth 200 cm. Profile B was dug 60 cm due the encountered bedrock, Profile C was dug to 80 cm due to water table at this depth. All the Profiles had area of 30,000cm². Each

pedon was described morphologically following the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) standards (Schoeneberger *et al.*, 2012). Pedogenic soil horizons were identified and sampled. Disturbed soil samples were collected for analyses. Also, undisturbed soil samples (core samples) using standard core samplers (99.6 cm³ by volume) were collected for the analyses of selected soil physical properties, from each genetic horizon. The soil samples taken were taken to the soil science laboratory for the determination of selected physical and chemical properties.

Plate 2 Profile A

Plate 3 Profile B

Plate 4 Profile C

Soil Physical Properties Determination

Particle size distribution (PSD) < 2 mm were determined using (Bouyoucos, 1962). Sodium hydroxide was used as dispersant. The textural classes were read out from the USDA soil textural triangle, while Bulk density was determined by the core and excavation methods described by Landon (1981).

Soil bulk density = oven dry weight of soil/volume of soil. Eq. 1

The moisture content was determined gravimetrically (Brady and Weil, 2002).

Soil porosity was calculated with the values of the bulk density using the method outlined by Brady and Weil (2002).

Soil total porosity (%) = 100 - (bulk density/Particle density x 100)Eq. 2

Soil Chemical Characteristics

Soil pH was determined in water and 1N KCl solution using a soil solution ratio of 1:2.5 with the aid of a glass electrode pH meter (McLean, 1982). Organic carbon was determined by wet dichromate acid oxidation method (Nelson and Sommers, 1982). Total nitrogen was estimated by the macro-kjeldahl digestion method (Bremner

and Mulvaney, 1982). Available phosphorus was obtained using Bray II bicarbonate extraction method (Olsen and Sommers, 1982), using 0.03 N ammonium fluoride with 0.1N HCl. The phosphorus in the extract was determined with a photo-electric colorimeter. Exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) were extracted with 1N NH₄OAc (pH 7.0) using 1:10 soil solution ratio. Potassium and sodium in the extract were determined with Flame Photometer while the exchangeable Ca and Mg were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Thomas, 1982).

The titration method, as outlined in Selected Methods for soil and plant analysis (Thomas, 1982), was used in the determination of the exchangeable acidity. The samples were extracted with 1N KCl solution and the

extract titrated with 0.05 NaOH. The Base saturation values were calculated as the percentage of exchangeable cations in the CEC.

Suitability Evaluation for Yam Cultivation

The suitability of the soils for yam was evaluated using the qualitative (non-parametric) methods (Akamigbo, 2010). The qualitative approach involved the matching of the crop requirements with the soil characteristics. This approach involves the numerical rating of some selected land qualities on a scale of 0 to 100 indicating very low to optimum values (Table 1), and according to the intended land utilization type (Yam Cultivation). The ratings were referenced to the established land requirements for the target crop (Table 2).

Table 1 *Class rates of soil suitability classes and agricultural uses*

Classes	Suitability classes	Rates
Class 1 (S₁)	Highly Suitable	85-100
Class 2 (S₂)	Moderately Suitable	84-60
Class 3 (S₃)	Marginally Suitable	59-40
Class4 (N₁)	Currently Not Suitable	39-20
Class 5 (N₂)	Permanently Not Suitable	<20

Adapted from Ukabiala (2022)

Table 2 Land/Crop requirements for rain-fed yam cultivation

Land qualities	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	N ₁	N ₂
	(100-85)	(84-60)	(59-40)	(39-20)	(19-0)
Climate (c):					
Annual rainfall (mm)	1000-1800	600-1000	500-600	400	<400
Length dry season (months)	3-5	5-6	6-7	any	>7
Mean annual temperature (°C)	20-30	>30	any	any	any
Topography (t):					
Slope (%)	0-8	8-16	16-30	30-50	>50
Wetness (w):					
Drainage	Well	Moderate	Poor	Very poor	Non- drainable
Soil physical properties (s):					
Texture	L, SCL,SL,SiC, SiCL,CL,SiL,SC	LFS, LS, FS	C, FS	any	Si
Coarse fragments (Vol %) 0 – 10 cm	<3	<15	<35	any	>35
Soil Depth (cm)	>100	>75	>50	any	<50
Fertility (f):					
CEC (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	>16	10-16	3-9	<3	any
Base saturation (%)	>35	20-35	10-19	<10	any
Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹), 0-15 cm	8-15	5-7	3-6	1-2	<1
pH (H ₂ O)	5.5 -7.5	5.0 – 5.5/7.5 -8.0	4.0 -4.9/8.0 -8.5	4.0/8.0	<4.0; >8.0
Total N (%)	>0.15	0.10 - 0.15	0.08 - 0.10	0.04 – 0.08	<0.04
Available P (mg kg ⁻¹)	>22	13 - 22	7 -13	3 - 7	<3
Exchangeable K (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	>0.5	0.3 -0.5	0.2 – 0.3	0.1 - 0.2	<0.1
Exchangeable Ca (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	10-15	5-10	1-5	< 1; > 5	any
Exchangeable Mg (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	2-5	1-2	< 1	< 1; > 5	any

CL= clay loam; SL= Sandy loam; SCL= sandy clay loam; L= loam; LFS=loamy fine sand; C= clay; Si=Silt; FS=Fine sand; SiCL= Silty clay loam; SiL= Silty loam
P= Phosphorus; K= Potassium; Ca= Calcium; Mg= Magnesium; N= Nitrogen; CEC= Cation exchange capacity
Modified from Sys (1985)

Data Analysis

The quantitative data generated from the laboratory analyses were subjected T-Test statistics at 95% confidence for the surface and subsurface soil layers. The P-values obtained were used as tests for statistical significance of the measured values across the toposequence.

Results and Discussion

The morphological, physical and chemical properties of soils of Amainyi-nta Toposequence are presented in Tables 3 to 5. There is clear evidence of developed argillic horizons in PROFILE A which occurred on the upland. The variations of brownish and reddish colours of PROFILE A is clear expression of braunification, rubifaction and ferrugination in the surface and subsurface horizons (Brady and Weil, 2002). There is no development of argillic horizons in PROFILE B due the bedrock encountered at 60 cm depth. The surface horizons ranged from granular to crumb soil structure.

These soils were non-sticky and non-plastic. The accumulation of clay in the sub-surface horizons gave rise to the dominant sub-angular blocky (sbk) soil structure. Water table was encountered at the depth of 80 cm in PROFILE C. The presence of possible fluctuating water table at this layer will limit root establishment at this layer. The

morphological findings are similar to the findings in Ukabiala (2019).

The physical properties of Amainyi-nta Toposequence is presented in Table 4. The results showed the textural classes of the pedons ranged from sandy loam to sandy clay loam. The bulk densities were moderate while the moisture content was low through the pedons, which may be as a result of the time of sampling (December). The upper parts of the soil profiles in this season are always low in moisture. However, the higher moisture content observed in Profile C is due to low elevation and high water table (Depth the water table = 60 cm). Toposequence may have influenced the variations observed in the sand ($p = 0.002$), Clay ($p = 0.023$) and bulk density ($p = 0.008$) of the surface soils. The general trend of the porosity is that it decrease down the profiles. However, the P-values of 0.003 and 0.004 obtained for the surface and subsurface soils respectively of the pedons, are clear indications of variation which may be attributed to the toposequential effect. According to Ukabiala (2022), variations in soil physical properties of soils can have profound implications for soil management, agricultural productivity, and environmental sustainability. The accumulation of sediments eroded from higher areas has always led finer textures at the foot slopes (Brady and Weil, 2002).

Table 5 shows the chemical characteristics of soil of Amainyi-nta Toposequence. The soils are slightly acidic but low in organic carbon, organic matter and total nitrogen. Available phosphorus levels greater than 14 mg/kg were measured in the surface and subsurface soils of Profile A. The exchangeable cations were low while a moderately high value of exchangeable calcium ($4.50 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$) was obtained in the surface soil of Profile C which may be due to mineralization of deposited material since this profile is on a lower slope. The cation exchange capacity of the soils were low to moderate while the base saturations were high, suggesting that high percentage of the soil's cation exchange capacity is occupied by the non-acid forming cations. Chemical

parameters including soil pH, organic carbon, organic matter, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, exchangeable calcium, and sodium, exchangeable acidity and cation exchange capacity significantly varied across the slope positions in the surface layers. This confirms the fact that topography or relief as a factor of soil formation exerts much influence the characteristics of soils that are formed (Brady and Weil, 2002). In the sub-surface soils, it is also observed that soil pH, total nitrogen, exchangeable acidity as well as base saturation had P-values less than 0.005, which could also be interpreted that the standard deviation varied widely from the mean.

Table 3 Morphological characteristics of soils of Amainyi-nta Toposequence

Pedon	Horizon depth (cm)	Horizon designation	Colour		Texture	Structure	Consistence		Boundary	Pores	Roots	Others
			Matrix				Wet	Moist				
PROFILE A	0-17	Ap1	2.5Y3/3	Dark olive brown	sl	26g	nsnp	fr	aw	cfi	cfi	-
	17-45	Ap2	10YR4/6	Dark yellowish brown	sl	26c	nsnp	f	cw	cfi	cfi	-
	45-120	Bt ₁	10R4/8	Red	scl	25sbk	sssp	f	gs	ffi	cfi	-
	120-200	Bt ₂	10R4/6	Red	sc	25sbk	sp	f		fvfi	-	-
PROFILE B	0-21	Ap1	10YR4/6	Dark yellowish brown	sl	24c	nsnp	f	cs	ffi	cfi	-
	21-38	Ap2	10YR5/6	Yellowish brown	scl	24sbk	sssp	f	gs	ffi	ffi	-
	38-60	B	10YR5/8	Yellowish brown	scl	26sbk	sp	v		-	-	Bed-rock
PROFILE C	0-10	Ap1	7.5YR3/2	Dark brown	scl	35c	sssp	l	gs	cfi	cfi	-
	10-30	Ap2	7.5YR3/3	Dark brown	scl	36sbk	sssp	l	gs	ffi	cfi	-
	30-80	Bcs	2.5YR4/4	Olive brown	ls	36sbk	sssp	fr		cfi	fvfi	Water Table

Structure: 2= moderate, 3= strong, 4= fine, 5= medium, 6= coarse, c= crumb, g= granular, sbk= subangular, s= single grain

Texture: l= loam, s= sand, c= clay, si= silt, cl= clay loam, sl= sandy loam, scl= sandy clay loam, sc= sandy clay, g= gravelly, v= very, e= extremely, st= stony

Consistence: sp= sticky and plastic, sssp= slightly sticky and slightly plastic, nsnp= non sticky and non plastic, l= loose, vfr= very friable, fr= friable, f= firm, v=very firm.

Pores and Roots: f= few, v= very, m= many, c=common, fi= fine, me= medium, co= coarse

Boundary: a= abrupt, c= clear, g= gradual, d= diffuse, s= smooth, w= wavy

Table 4 Selected Physical Properties of Amainyi-nta Toposequence

Pedon	Depth (cm)	Horizon designation	Sand	Silt	Clay	Textural class	Bulk Density g/cm ³	Moisture Content (%)	Porosity (%)
			------(%)-----						
PROFILE A	0-17	Ap1	61.52	20.28	18.20	sl	0.80	6.60	69.80
	17-45	Ap2	62.52	19.49	17.99	sl	1.41	2.24	47.00
	45-120	Bt ₁	63.52	3.28	33.20	scl	1.62	7.51	38.90
	120-200	Bt ₂	57.52	1.28	41.20	sc	1.69	9.65	37.00
PROFILE B	0-21	Ap1	60.52	21.81	17.67	sl	1.05	4.70	61.00
	21-38	Ap2	65.52	7.28	27.20	scl	1.55	11.27	42.00
	38-60	B	69.52	5.28	25.20	scl	1.64	9.51	39.00
PROFILE C	0-10	Ap1	68.52	3.71	27.77	scl	1.09	25.12	59.00
	10-30	Ap2	70.53	3.19	26.28	scl	1.32	21.41	51.00
	30-80	Bcs	81.52	7.20	11.28	ls	1.45	24.64	46.00
Surface P -value			0.002	0.119	0.023		0.008	0.203	0.003
Subsurface P-value			0.010	0.119	0.096		0.002	0.101	0.004

ls= loamy sand, sc= sandy clay, scl= sandy clay loam, sl= sandy loam, p<0.05 (2-tailed)

Table 5 Chemical Characteristics of Soils of Amainyi-nta Toposequence

Pedon	Depth (cm)	Horizon designation	pH (H ₂ O)	OC	OM	TN	C:N	Av. P (mg kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable cations				Exchangeable Acidity (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	CEC	BS (%)
									Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺			
PROFILE A	0-17	Ap1	6.02	1.52	2.61	0.26	5.85	16.32	2.60	1.14	0.12	0.42	0.64	4.92	86.99
	17-45	Ap2	5.35	0.20	0.34	0.18	1.11	13.79	2.20	1.07	0.05	0.37	0.60	4.29	86.01
	45-120	Bt ₁	5.35	0.30	0.52	0.17	1.76	14.01	2.10	0.96	0.04	0.38	0.70	4.18	83.25
	120-200	Bt ₂	5.20	1.22	2.09	0.19	6.42	14.50	2.00	0.94	0.08	1.19	0.72	4.93	85.40
PROFILE B	0-21	Ap1	5.20	1.58	2.72	0.33	4.79	17.29	2.75	1.16	0.18	0.55	0.80	5.44	85.29
	21-38	Ap2	5.10	0.20	0.34	0.18	1.11	16.08	2.70	1.08	0.11	0.43	0.94	5.26	82.13
	38-60	B	5.00	0.48	0.83	0.19	2.53	2.15	0.96	0.05	0.65	13.91	0.83	16.4	94.94
PROFILE C	0-10	Ap1	6.04	1.26	2.34	0.22	5.73	15.11	4.50	2.36	0.46	0.86	1.30	9.48	86.29
	10-30	Ap2	5.94	1.26	2.17	0.20	6.30	14.00	3.13	1.59	0.17	0.55	0.70	6.14	88.60
	30-80	Bcs	5.75	0.42	0.72	0.20	2.10	13.33	2.91	1.35	0.08	0.42	0.40	5.16	92.25
Surface P-value			0.002	0.005	0.002	0.014	0.004	0.002	0.033	0.061	0.137	0.043	0.044	0.044	0.000
Subsurface P-value			0.002	0.111	0.110	0.000	0.116	0.126	0.074	0.179	0.291	0.358	0.037	0.145	0.001

OC= Organic carbon, OM= Organic Matter, TN= Total Nitrogen, Av. P= Available Phosphorus, Ca²⁺= Exchangeable Calcium, Mg²⁺= Exchangeable Magnesium, K⁺= Exchangeable Potassium, Na⁺= Exchangeable Sodium, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity, BS = Base Saturation, p<0.05 (2-tailed)

Suitability of the Pedons for Yam Cultivation

The Profiles A, B and C were evaluated to be marginally suitable for Yam cultivation. Though there were variations in the parameters measured, on average the Pedons are potentially good for yam cultivation (See Table 1). Profile A has aggregate score of 80 (the highest). This may be

as a result of favourable drainage class and pH of the soil. Poor drainage condition may have influenced the low level of Profile C. It has been reported that yam cultivated in poorly drained soil are more prone to diseases. Also, there may be issues of nutrient imbalances (Ukabiala, 2022).

Table 6 Suitability Class Scores of the Soils of Amainyi-nta Toposequence

Land qualities/units	Profile A	Profile B	Profile C
Climate (c):	90	90	90
Annual rainfall (mm)	95	95	95
Length dry season (months)	80	80	80
Mean annual temperature (°C)	90	90	90
Topography (t):			
Slope (%)	100	100	100
Wetness (w):			
Drainage	90	80	30
Soil physical properties (s):			
Texture	90	90	60
Soil Depth (cm)	90	30	40
Fertility (f):			
CEC (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	40	60	90
Base saturation (%)	80	90	80
Organic carbon (g kg ⁻¹), 0-15cm	80	70	50
pH (H ₂ O)	80	50	80
Total N (g kg ⁻¹)	80	70	50
Available P (mg kg ⁻¹)	80	70	60
Exchangeable K (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	40	70	70
Exchangeable Ca (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	60	60	80
Exchangeable Mg (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	70	80	90
AGGREGATE SUITABILITY SCORE	80 (S₂)	76 (S₂)	74 (S₂)

Ca= Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, K = Potassium, P = Phosphorus, N = Nitrogen, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity, S₁ = Highly Suitable, S₂ = Moderately Suitable, S₃ = Marginally Suitable, N₁ = Not Currently Suitable, N₂ = Permanently not suitable

Conclusion

This research was aimed at discovering the effect of toposequence on the suitability of soils of Amainyi-nta in Ihitte/Uboma local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria for the cultivation of

yam. It was discovered that some of the physico-chemical properties of the soils including soil texture, bulk density, soil pH. Organic carbon, organic matter, total nitrogen as well as base saturation were influence by the toposequence. This validates the claim that topography is one

the major factors of soil formation. Nevertheless, the suitability evaluation of the soils across the toposequence showed that the soils fall within the suitability class of Moderately Suitable (S_2) for yam cultivation. All the pedons used for this research had one limiting factor or the other. For instance, The Profile C was highly limited by high fluctuating water table. Management options that can improve the soils of Profile A and Profile B will include adequate addition of organic matter to improve the limiting factors while Profile C will require artificial drainage system to take care of the fluctuating water table. Large heaps/mounds can also be of help in talking the drainage problems within this pedon, in order to optimally cultivate yam. Another option is timing of planting, that is, timing planting to avoid the season of groundwater research.

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References

- Adegbenro, R. O., Ojetade, J. O., Oguntade, O. A., Blessing, O. O., & Faturoti, O. M. (2024). Characterization and suitability assessment of soils underlain by mica-schist for yam and cocoyam production in rainforest area Southwestern, Nigeria. *EQA - International Journal of Environmental Quality*, 60, 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2281-4485/18723>
- Aini, L.N., Prasetyo, J., Nuru, S.N Makiyah and Mulyono (2021). valuation of land suitability for Yam (*Dioscorea alata*) in Cangkringan, Sleman, Special Region of Yogyakarta. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 1 -8., DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/752/1/012029.
- Akamigbo, F.O.R. (2010). *Fundamental Methods of Soil Resource Survey, Classification, Interpretation and Application*. University of Nigeria. Press Ltd, UNN, pp81.
- Atofarati, S.O., Ewulo, B.S and Ojeniyi, S.O. (2012). Characterization and classification of soils on two toposequence at Ile-Oluji, Ondo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of AgriScience* 2(7): 642-650
- Bassey, E.E. (2017). Constraints and prospects of yam production in Nigeria, *European Journal of Physical and Agricultural Sciences* 5(1):55 - 54
- Bouyoucos, G.J. (1962). Hydrometer Method Improved for Making Particle Size Analysis of Soils. *Agronomy Journal*. 54:464-465.
- Brady, N.C. and Weil, R.R. (2002). *The Nature and Properties of Soils*. Pearson Education, Inc. New Jessy, USA.
- Bremmer, J.M. and Mulvaney, C.S. (1982). Total nitrogen, pp895-926. In Page *et al.* (eds). *Methods of Soil Analysis*. Part 2. 2nd ed. *Agronomy Monograph* 9, ASA and Soil Science Society of America, Madison WI.
- Buol, S.W., Hole, F.D. and McCracken, R.J. (1973). *Soil Genesis and Classification*. The Iowa State University Press, USA, pp65.

- Carter, M.R. (Ed.) (1993). *Soil Sampling and Methods of Analysis*. Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, Florida. pp 368.
- Chikezie, P.C., Ibegbulem, C.O. and Stella, M. (2016). Amino Acid Profiles, Total Nitrogen Contents, and Computed-Protein Efficiency Ratios of Manihot esculenta Root and Dioscorea rotundata Tuber Peels. *Journal of Food Processing*, 5(8)1-1. DOI:10.1155/2016/1697458.
- Ezeaku, P.I. (2011). *Methodologies for Agricultural Land-Use Planning – Sustainable Soil Management and Productivity*. Great AP Express Publishers Ltd, Nsukka, Nigeria. pp69.
- Fasina, A.S., Raji, A., Oluwatosin, G.A., Omoju, O.J. and Oluwadare, D.A. (2015). Properties, genesis, classification, capability and sustainable management of soils from South-Western Nigeria. *International Journal of Soil Science*10: 142-152
- IITA (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture), (2013). Report, achievement, challenges and prospects of yam production in Nigeria, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Jenny, H. (1958) Factors of Soil Formation. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Klute, A. and Dirksen, C. (1986). Hydraulic conductivity and diffusivity laboratory methods. In Klute, A. Ed. *Methods of Soil Analyses*. American Society of Agronomy-Soil Science Society of America, Madison, pp635-662.
- Landon, J.R. (ed). (1981). *Booker Tropical Soil Manual*. Booker Agricultural International Ltd. London. 78-80.
- Lin, Y.S., Chen, Y.G., Chen, Z.S., and Hsieh, M.L. (2005). Soil morphological variations on the Taoyuan Terrace, Northwestern Taiwan: Roles of topography and groundwater. *Geomorphology* 69: 138-151
- McLean, E.O. (1982). Soil pH and Lime Requirement. P. 199-224. In: Page *et al.*(eds) *Method of Soil Analysis part 2. Chemical and Microbial Properties*. 2nd 288 ed. Agronomy Monograph 9, ASA and SSSA, Madison WI.
- Nelson, D.W. and Sommers, C.E. (1982). Total carbon, organic carbon and organic matter, In: A.C. Page and C.A. Black (eds). *Methods of Soil Analysis Part 2*, 2nd ed. *Agronomic Monograph* 9 ASA and SSA, Madison, W.I. pp. 539 – 579.
- Nuga, B.O. and Akinbola, G.E. (2010). Soil Survey Information for Sustainable Agriculture in Ikwuano Local Government Area, Abia State, South East, Nigeria. Second RUFORUM Biennial Meeting, 20th - 24th September, 2010, Entebbe, Uganda.
- Ogunkunle, A.O. (1993). Soil in land suitability evaluation: an example with oil palm in Nigeria. *Soil Use and Management*, 9(1):35-40.
- Ogunkunle, A.O. (2005). Soil survey and sustainable land management. Invited paper at the 29th annual conference of soil science society of Nigeria held at University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, from 6th to 10th December, 2004.
- Ogunkunle, O. (2013). A comparative study of the physical and chemical properties of soils under different vegetation types. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 3(1):24-28.
- Olson, S.R. and Sommers, L.E. (1982). Phosphorus. pp403-434. In Page *et al.* (eds). *Methods of Soil Analysis. Part 2. Agronomy*

Monograph 9, ASA and Soil Science Society of America, Madison WI.

Monograph 9. ASA and SSSA, Madison, WI.

- Rhoades, J.D. (1982). Cation exchange capacity
In: Page, A.L. (Ed.), *Methods of Soil Analysis Part 2*. 2nd Edition, Agronomy Monograph 9. ASA, Madison, W.I. pp403-434.
- Samndi, M. A. and Adamu, J. (2010). Influence of topography on soil morphological and physical properties on the newer basalts of the Jos Plateau, Nigeria. *Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 3(2): 170 – 176.
- Schoeneberger, P.J., D.A. Wysocki, E.C. Benham, and Soil Survey Staff. (2012). *Field book for describing and sampling soils*, Version 3.0. Natural Resources Conservation Service, National Soil Survey Center, Lincoln, NE.
- Soil Survey Staff (1999). *Soil Taxonomy: A Basic System of Soil Classification for Making and Interpreting Soil Surveys*. Second Edition. United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, Agriculture Handbook, Number 436.
- Tertsea, I., Martha, H.G. and Fanan, U (2022). Suitability Analysis for Yam Production in Nigeria using Satellite and Observation Data. *Journal of the Nigerian Society of Physical Sciences*, 4(4), 883. <https://doi.org/10.46481/jnsps.2022.883>
- Thomas, G.W. (1982). Exchangeable cations, pp 159 – 165. In: Page *et al.* (eds) *Methods of Soil Analysis*. Part 2. 2nd . *Agronomy Monograph 9*. ASA and SSSA, Madison, WI.
- Udoh, B.T., Henry, H.B. and Akpa, U.S. (2011). Suitability evaluation of alluvial soils for rice (*Oryza Sativa*) and cocoa (*Theobroma Cacao*) cultivation in an acid sands area of southern Nigeria. *Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering and Science*, 2(3):148-161.
- Ukabiala, M. E., Kefas, P. K. Akpan-Idiok, A. U., Philip, H. J., Ngasoh, F. G. and Kefas, A. P. (2016). Assessment of the Physicochemical Characteristics, Degradation Rate and Vulnerability Potential of Ihitte/Uboma Soils, Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture and Environmental Research*. 2(5): 1467-1479. DOI: [10.3923/ijar.2012.358.366](https://doi.org/10.3923/ijar.2012.358.366)
- Ukabiala, M.E. and Obazi, S.A. (2022). Characterization and Suitability Evaluation of Upland Soils for Maize, Cassava and Oil Palm Production, in Kogi East, Nigeria. *J Soil Water Sci* 6(1):278-285. DOI: 10.36959/624/454
- Versus (2024). Yam and Cassava, <https://versus.com/en/cassava-vs-yam>. Retrieved on Tuesday, 11/06/2024 by 1 pm.
- Yannis, G. D, Satish, B., Rafael, L. B., Sharon, A. B., Daniel, M., and Daniel, D. R. (2016). Topographic variability and the influence of soil erosion on the carbon cycle, *Advancing Earth and Space Sciences*, 30(5):644-660 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GB005302>